

Join our BioBlitz and see what biodiversity we have in the park!

- 1** Welcome Table in Courtyard
Available 11am-3pm
- 2** Vegetation Safari
3 min walk from courtyard
11.15, 12.15, 12.45, 13.15, 13.45, 14.15
- 3** Wonderful Worms and Super Soil
10 min walk from Courtyard
11.15, 11.45, 12.45, 13.15, 13.45, 14.15

- 4** Marvelous Minibeasts
5 min walk from Courtyard
11.15, 11.45, 12.15, 13.15, 13.45, 14.15
- 5** Brilliant Birds
5 min walk from courtyard
11.15, 11.45, 12.15, 12.45, 13.45, 14.15

Suggested areas to explore using the iNaturalist app
Available 11am-3pm

Once you collect a sticker from each station come back to the courtyard to complete your mission!

Vegetation Safari

This Project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 862731

Wonderful Worms and Super Soil

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Marvellous Minibeasts

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Brilliant Birds

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BIOBLITZ PASSPORT

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